

THEORETICAL BASIS OF ACHIEVING A POSITIVE EFFECTIVENESS OF MENTAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHILDREN WITH AUTISM THROUGH MUSIC (CELLO)

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Abstract: This scientific article provides detailed information about the scientific and theoretical basis of improving the mental state of children with autism through music in their treatment. Also, the positive features of organizing the treatment process using the wide use of musical instruments, especially the cello, are highlighted.

Key words: Autism, music, psychological characteristics, classical music, teenagers, illness, cello, musical ability, creativity.

Music – it's not just something we listen to, it's also something that relieves pain, relieves stress, helps you understand yourself, and breaks down communication barriers.

It is known that favorite music can even reduce pain. In one experiment, scientists examined the effects of listening to music on the ability to tolerate unpleasant sensations and pain. They invited 54 people to their experiment. The participants had to pass the test with cold water. In particular, they had to hold their hands in cold water until they felt severe pain. Each participant has to pass the test 3 times: in the first, they listen to their favorite songs during the process, in the second, they listen to special relaxation music selected by scientists, and in the third, they listen to loud noise. It turned out that people can endure pain more than anything else after listening to their favorite song. That's why many people put on their favorite tracks while running or working out in the gym - a relaxing soundtrack is actually more durable - increases tolerance and subjectively reduces pain.

Playing music helps people with various intellectual and mental disabilities and autism to better adapt and integrate into society. Music is also used in hospitals to help patients reduce pain and release stress from serious procedures.

Music is a method of psychotherapy based on emotional perception of music using the influence of music in the treatment, rehabilitation, education and upbringing of children and adults suffering from physical and mental diseases.

Based on the rhythmic basis of the melody and its performance, music has different effects on people depending on their individual inner experiences and feelings. Music can be used to influence human mood. Music is an ancient and natural method that most people use to relieve psychological stress, calm down and concentrate, and improve their emotional state.

The purpose of using music therapy in children with autism : to develop and correct the process of emotional perception (sensing, perceiving, demonstrating), strengthening movement, in cases of arrest in speech activity (removing anxiety caused by a sudden change in social and personal status) is to create a positive-emotional environment of rehabilitation

At this point, we refer to Karl Koenig's approach to healing diseases through music: In order for music to have a deep effect on the body, the patient himself must be active (sing, play musical instruments, express music in his movements). We see the essence of music in the potential of "special" children, which has a positive and healing effect on mental development and emotional processes, and directs the child's reserve power to self-management in all areas of art and in life in general.

Experts divide the treatment of children with autism through music into passive and active forms. First, patients are encouraged to listen to a variety of music that is relevant to their mental health and healing process. Those who have communicated with disabled children at least once know how difficult it is to find a way to their hearts. Therefore, the naturalness and potential of music has been one of the reasons for the rapid development of treatment of children with autism through music in the last 2-3 decades.

The benefits of music in shaping the health of autistic children in a positive way are as follows:

- ❖ helps to strengthen trust and mutual understanding between the participants of the process;
- ❖ helps speed up the healing process, because inner experiences are expressed more easily through music than through conversation;
- ❖ music activates emotions, serves as a means of enhancing conscious perception;
- ❖ indirectly improves musical skills, the process of self-control and regulation of thoughts appears.

The earlier Music Therapy is started, the more likely it is to be successful. Therefore, children with disabilities can be treated and developed with the help of music from the age of two. In two-year-old children, the scope of imagination about the external world is very narrow, speech is not well developed, the nervous system, auditory and visual senses are weak, movements are not coordinated, attention is unstable. Usually, such children do not have the skills and abilities to imitate sounds, sing and pronounce simple musical tones. Children do not know how to coordinate their movements with music, they cannot react to external signals with their actions by hearing and seeing. But they have imitative features, which is manifested in musical-rhythmic movements, humming and singing.

We should also say that we will be able to have a positive effect on children faster through the use of musical instruments and live performances. Especially the works performed on the cello are very effective. As an example, D. D. Shostakovich's concertos for Cello and orchestra. This music has a positive emotional effect on a person, helps children to reveal their minds and feelings, and to develop creative skills.

The benefits of cello music for children with autism include:

1. Absolute indifference;
2. Ease and convenience of use;
3. Ability to control;
4. Ability to reduce the need to use other treatment methods that require a lot of time and pressure.

Music organized according to the laws of psychophysiological effects can be successfully reflected and manifested with the help of a specially organized composition of sound combinations:

- ✓ Different moods, joy, happiness, cheerfulness, sadness, gentleness, depression, confidence, anxiety;
- ✓ Intellectual and volitional processes-perseverance, zeal, pressure, care, mobility, lack of will, seriousness;
- ✓ Appearance of the generalized characteristics of existence - strength, lightness, duration, direction, width, spatiality;
- ✓ Characteristics of variety of movements - fast, moderate, slow, elastic, strong, loose, flexible.

Musical rhythmicity is used in the treatment of disorders of support and speech activity (in autism, stuttering, incoherence of movement, stopping), sense of

rhythm, speech, and breathing. In preschool children, it is manifested in the form of small group activities, such as rhythmic games, breathing exercises, performing a specific rhythm at an accelerated and decelerated pace.

We will consider two types of music therapy: methods using instruments (cello) and singing musical works. The first round includes the following stages:

- diagnostics;
- choosing a group of tools suitable for the child's problem;
- choosing a musical instrument from the group preferred by the child;
- offer to listen and choose musical parts in the performance of each of these instruments;
- determining the list of works performed by musical instruments chosen by children;
- final stage.

Treatment with the help of musical works includes the following stages:

- diagnostics;
- selection of musical works;
- selection of the final work.

In special education, it is possible to organize activities with children using musical works and musical instruments. It is recommended to use classical music in this process. You can choose the following works for listening written by Bach, Liszt, Chopin, Rachmaninoff, Beethoven, Mozart, Tchaikovsky, Schubert, D.D. Shostakovich and others

Technology of conducting music therapy using cello:

First of all, as a specialist and a psychologist, it is necessary to diagnose the child's condition, to choose a musical composition according to the child, determining his emotional state. After diagnosis and identification of problems, it is necessary to choose a group of tools suitable for the child's problem, after which it is determined which of several tools is preferable. This can be solved in the following ways:

- a child or teenager chooses a musical instrument from the group he prefers;
- Listen to a part of the works performed by each of the selected musical instruments and offer to make a choice;
- Listening to pieces of music performed by the cello. A high-impact musical instrument is chosen.

From the work of a number of scientists, we can see that music therapy includes a system of various differentiated methods, some of which are traditional, while others are modified based on the specific characteristics of speech disorders. In conclusion, we can say that the positive effect of treatment of autistic children using cello was recorded in various ways. These are patient observation and survey. Now the skill and culture of listening to soothing music has been formed. The main thing we can say is that the treatment of children with autism through the cello has shown a very positive effect.

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